

SPACE GROUP DETERMINATION OF THE CRYSTALS OF ORTHO- AND PARA- BENZTOLUIDES BY THE X-RAY ROTATING CRYSTAL METHOD.

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Rotation photographs gave the following dimensions of the unit cell :—

p-benztoluide ($a = 26.116$ A.U., $b = 9.117$ A.U., $c = 9.87$ A.U.),

o-benztoluide ($a = 30.54$ A.U., $b = 8.24$ A.U., $c = 9.246$ A.U.).

Oscillation photographs taken about three principal axes at suitable small angles gave halvings corresponding to the space Q_1' for the first and Q_1'' for the second.

1-o-Benztoluide.

o-Benztoluide crystallises from a mixture of ethylacetate and acetone in the rhombic class with the $m\{100\}$, $a\{100\}$, $c\{001\}$ and $r\{101\}$ faces. The axial ratio is $a : b : c = 1.8449 : 1 : 0.2810$ (*cf.* Groth, "Chemische Krystallographie," V, p. 165)

The substance was prepared by condensing benzoyl chloride with *o*-toluidine in an alkaline medium. The product was crystallised from methylated spirit. Suitable crystals were obtained by recrystallising the pure substance from a mixture of ethyl acetate and alcohol. The crystals were colourless, transparent and prismatic in shape. The melting point was found to be 143.44° . The substance was found to become dull on exposure to the atmosphere.

A Shearer gas-tube with copper target ($\lambda = 1.54$) was used as the source of X-rays. Usually the $m\{110\}$ faces had developed well on the crystals and the rotation photograph about the *c*-axis (Plate I) was easily obtained. The crystal was then suitably set so that the *a* and *b* axes were in turn coincident with the axis of rotation and the rotation photographs were taken (Plates II and III). On account of the unstability of the crystals rather short exposures were given.

The dimensions of the unit cell obtained from the rotation photographs are $a = 30.54$ A.U., $b = 8.24$ A.U., $c = 9.246$ A.U.

The axial ratio agrees closely with that given in Groth (*loc. cit.*).

$$\left. \begin{aligned} a : b : c &:: 3.707 : 1 : 1.122 \\ &:: 2(1.854) : 1 : 4(0.2805) \\ &:: 1.8469 : 1 : 0.2810 \end{aligned} \right\} \begin{array}{l} \text{Author's} \\ \text{Groth,} \end{array}$$

except that $a : b$ is doubled and $c : b$ is quadrupled.

Oscillation photographs at suitable small angles were taken about all the three crystallographic axes and the spots indexed with the help of Bernal's charts. The planes identified have been collected and classified under different heads in Tables I and II.

TABLE I.

Axial planes.			Prism planes.				
Planes.	Intensity.	hol.	Intensity.	okl.	Intensity.	hko.	Intensity.
002	v.s.	102	m.s.	012	v.w.	210	v.s.
004	w.m.	104	v.m.	013	v.w.	220	m.
020	v.w.	202	m.s.	014	v.w.	230	v.w.
200	m.	204	m.	021	v.s.	410	s.
400	v.s.	302	s.	022	w.	420	w.
600	s.	402	s.	032	v.w.	430	v.w.
800	w.	404	m.	033	w.	610	v.s.
(10)00	m.s.	502	s.	041	w.m.	620	m.
(12)00	w.	504	m.			630	w.
(14)00	v.w.	602	v.s.			810	v.s.
		604	w.m.			820	m.s.
		702	v.s.			(10)10	w.
		704	m.			(10)20	w.
		802	w.			(10)30	w.m.
		902	w.			(12)10	v.w.
		(10)02	v.w.			(14)10	v.w.
		(10)04	m.			(14)20	v.w.
		(11)02	m.				
		(12)02	w.				
		(12)04	v.w.				
		(13)02	m.s.				
		(13)04	m.				

TABLE II.

General planes.

Planes.	Intensity.	Planes	Intensity.	Planes.	Intensity.	Planes.	Intensity.
111	m.s.	322	m.s.	612	m.	921	v.w.
112	m.	332	v.w.	613	m.	922	v.w.
113	v.w.	333	w.	614	m.s.	923	w.
121	m.s.	341	v.w.	622	m.	932	v.w.
122	m.	342	v.w.	623	v.s.	(10)11	w.m.
123	v.w.	411	w.	631	w.m.	(10)12	w.m.
131	v.w.	412	m.	711	w.m.	(10)13	w.m.
132	v.w.	413	m.	713	v.w.	(10)21	m.
133	w.	414	w.	721	m.s.	(10)22	v.w.
211	m.s.	421	s.	722	m.	(10)23	v.w.
212	m.s.	422	m.	731	m.s.	(10)32	v.w.
213	w.	432	v.w.	732	v.w.	(11)11	m.
214	w.	433	v.w.	733	v.w.	(11)12	w.m.
221	m.	511	v.s.	811	m.	(11)13	v.w.
222	m.	512	m.	812	v.w.	(11)14	v.w.
231	w.m.	513	m.	813	v.w.	(11)22	w.
232	v.w.	521	s.	814	v.w.	(11)31	m.
241	v.w.	522	w.	823	w.	(12)11	w.
242	v.w.	523	v.w.	831	m.s.	(13)11	m.
311	v.s.	524	v.w.	833	w.	(13)12	m.
312	m.	531	w.	911	w.	(13)21	v.w.
313	w.	532	v.w.	912	v.w.	(15)12	v.w.
314	w.	542	v.w.	913	v.w.	(16)11	v.w.
321	m.s.	611	v.s.	914	v.w.		

The above tables show that $\{h0l\}$ planes are halved when l is odd and $\{hko\}$ are halved when h is odd. The crystals, therefore, belong to the space group Q_8^1 of the orthorhombic bipyramidal class.

The number of asymmetric units required to complete the symmetry of the cell is eight. The number calculated from the dimensions of the cell and the specific gravity of the crystals (1.205, Groth) is 8.005 (very nearly eight). Single molecules of *o*-benztoluide, therefore, form the asymmetric units of the cell.

p-Benzotoluide.

Crystals belong to the rhombic bipyramidal class and develop a {100}, l {410}, n {210}, o {111}, c {001} and s {302} faces. The axial ratio is

$$a : b : c :: 2.8067 : 1 : 1.0815 \text{ (Groth, } loc. cit., p. 166).$$

The substance was prepared in the same way as described in the previous section except that the *para*- instead of the *ortho*-toluidine was used. The pure substance melted at 157°.

Colourless, transparent and well developed crystals were obtained by the slow evaporation of the solution of the substance in a mixture of acetone and alcohol. The crystals which were prismatic along the *c*-axis were quite stable when exposed to the atmosphere and almost all the faces described in Groth were identified. Rotation photographs about the *a*, *b*, and the *c* axes gave the following dimensions (*vide* Plates IV, V and VI),

$$a = 26.11 \text{ \AA}, \quad b = 9.12 \text{ \AA}, \quad c = 9.87 \text{ \AA}.$$

The axial ratio is $a : b : c :: 2.863 : 1 : 1.082$ which agrees very well with that given in Groth. The following tables (III and IV) give the list of planes identified on the oscillation photographs about the three principal axes.

TABLE III.

Plane.	Axial planes.		Intensity.	okl.	Prism planes.		
	Intensity.	hol.			Intensity.	hko.	Intensity.
002	s.	102	s.	021	m.s.	210	m.s.
200	m.	202	m.	022	w.	220	w.m.
400	s.	204	w.m.	023	w.	230	w.
600	v.w.	302	m.s.	024	w.m.	410	m.
(10)00	m.s.	304	m.	041	m.	420	v.w.
(12)00	w.m.	402	m.s.	042	w.	430	w.m.
		404	m.	043	w.m.	440	w.
		502	m.s.			610	v.s.
		504	w.m.			620	w.m.
		602	m.s.			640	w.
		604	m.			810	m.s.
		702	m.s.			820	m.s.

TABLE III (contd.).

Prism planes.		hko. Intensity.	
hol.	Intensity.	hko.	Intensity.
704	m.	840	w.m.
802	w.m.	(10)20	w.m.
804	w.m.	(10)30	w.m.
902	w.m.	(12)10	w.
(10)04	w.	(12)20	w.
(12)02	v.w.	(14)10	v.w.
(13)02	w.m.	(14)20	v.w.

TABLE IV.

General planes.

Planes.	Intensity.	Planes.	Intensity.	Planes.	Intensity.
111	s.	342	w.m.	812	v.w.
113	w.m.	343	w.m.	813	w.
114	v.w.	412	m.	822	w.
121	m.	413	m.	823	w.
122	v.w.	414	w.	831	m.
123	w.m.	422	v.w.	833	v.w.
124	v.w.	424	w.	834	v.w.
133	w.m.	441	w.m.	841	v.w.
142	w.	443	w.	911	v.w.
211	w.m.	511	v.s.	912	w.
212	w.m.	512	w.	913	v.w.
213	m.	513	w.m.	921	v.w.
214	w.	521	m.s.	922	v.w.
221	m.	522	m.	923	v.w.
222	w.m.	524	v.w.	924	v.w.
224	w.	532	w.m.	931	w.
231	w.m.	534	w.	933	v.w.
232	w.	542	w.	941	v.
233	w.	543	w.	(10)11	w.m.

Planes.	Intensity.	Planes.	Intensity.	Planes.	Intensity.
241	w.	611	m.s.	(10)13	v.w.
242	w.	612	w.m.	(10)22	w.
243	w.	613	w.m.	(10)23	v.w.
251	v.w.	621	w.	(10)31	w.
311	s.	624	v.w.	(10)32	w.
312	m.s.	631	w.m.	(11)11	v.w.
313	w.m.	632	w.	(11)13	w.
314	w.m.	633	s.	(11)21	v.w.
321	m.s.	642	w.	(11)22	v.w.
322	w.	711	m.	(11)23	v.w.
324	v.w.	721	w.	(11)31	w.m.
331	w.	722	w.	(12)12	v.w.
332	w.	723	w.	(12)13	w.
333	w.	731	w.m.	(12)21	v.w.
334	v.w.	741	v.w.	(13)11	w.
341	w.	811	w.	(13)12	w.

It will be seen from the above tables that

(*okl*) planes are halved when *k* is odd :

(*hko*) ,, ,, ,, ,, *h* is odd ;

and (*hol*) ,, ,, ,, ,, 1 ,, ,, .

The halvings correspond to the space group Q_1^5 with Γ_0 Bravais lattice.

The number of molecules required by the space group is eight. The number calculated from the dimensions of the cell and the specific gravity of the crystals (1.202) is also eight (accurately 8.06). This shows that molecules of *p*-benzotoluide in the unit cell are asymmetric.

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Oscillation photographs of o-benzotoluide.

Plate I.
a-axis

Plate II.
b-axis

Plate III.
c-axis

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Oscillation photographs of p-benzofulide.

Plate IV.
a-axis

Plate V.
b-axis

Plate VI
c-axis

